

ADSORPTION OF CO₂ ON AMINE-GRAFTED ACTIVATED CARBON FIBER FABRICS

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Keywords: Activated carbon fibers, Amination, Characterization, Carbon dioxide, Adsorption

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the surface of activated carbon fibers (ACFs) were grafted with monoethanolamine (MEA) and N-[3-(trimethoxysilyl) propyl]ethylenediamine (TPEDA). The properties of the samples were characterized using FESEM, EA, TGA, XPS, and the measurements of N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms. The CO₂ adsorption isotherms of all samples were measured using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 system. The CO₂/N₂ selectivity was determined to understand the interaction strength with active adsorption sites. Finally, the Clausius-Clapeyron equation was used to calculate the isosteric heat of adsorption. Results showed that the amination reduced the specific surface area of ACFs but enhanced the adsorption selectivity for CO₂ adsorption. Modification with MEA or TPEDA increased the bulk N content in ACFs. Particularly, ACF modified with TPEDA exhibited the most abundant surface N atoms. Additionally, the graft of MEA onto oxidized ACFs was favorable to the fixation of nitrogen functional groups on the surface. The surface N-functionalities on ACFs were characterized by the pyridine-like structures of six-member rings, while pre-oxidation of ACFs would change the pyridine-like structures to the pyridone structures. The adsorption isotherms of CO₂ were indicative of physical adsorption and exothermic reactions. The uptakes of CO₂ at 25 °C and 101.3 kPa (1 atm) followed the order ACF (2.358 mmole/g) > cMEA-ACF (2.215 mmole/g) > TPEDA-ACF (2.098 mmole/g) > MEA-ACF (1.964 mmole/g). The Freundlich equations could be used to fit the adsorption data well and all indicated the favorable adsorption. The adsorption selectivity of CO₂ over N₂ was the best for the ACFs modified with MEA at 55 °C (~9.7). The data also showed the adsorption of CO₂ was occurred on the heterogeneous surfaces.

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasing CO₂ emission has leading to global warming and related climate change. For coal-fired power plants, the major flue gas components by volume are N₂ (70-75 %), CO₂ (15-16 %), H₂O (5-7 %), and O₂ (3-4 %), with total pressures near 1 bar and temperatures between 40 and 60 °C [1]. Control of atmospheric CO₂ level through post combustion capture is a potential option to mitigate the possible risks. The CO₂ capture and sequestration (CCS) is a set of technologies that can greatly reduce CO₂ emissions from new and existing emission sources and is considered as an effective approach in mitigating global warming. The capture technology is the most important for cost-effective removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere since the expenses during the capture processes account for about 70 % of all costs in CCS [2]. Various CO₂ capture technologies such as absorption, adsorption, cryogenics, and membranes have been widely investigated. Among them, the absorption-regeneration technologies have been recognized as the most effective methods, where the processes using ammonia-based or the amine-based absorbents have receiving the greatest attention [3]. However, the high energy density of the absorption processes has restricted their applications. In 2005, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) special report disclosed the adsorption methods might be promising processes to separate CO₂ from gas phase by choosing appropriate adsorbents [4]. In this respect, several possible adsorbents including activated carbon [5], activated carbon fibers (ACFs) [2], carbon molecular sieves [6], zeolite [7], silica adsorbents [8], or carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [9] have been considered as potential candidates for CO₂ capture.

Among of these well-known adsorbents, ACFs have the properties of small fiber diameters, large specific surface area, uniform pore size distributions and rapid adsorption/desorption rates, and have been widely used adsorbents. In order to improve the adsorption capacity of CO₂, the modification of ACFs is usually adapted. Amine-modified adsorbents have been successfully used for CO₂ adsorption from moist gas at low and moderate temperatures. The adsorption amounts of CO₂ on CNTs and CNTs modified by 3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane (APTS) decreased with temperature, but increased with water content in air at 0-7 % [9]. Mesoporous spherical-silica particles modified with N-[3-(trimethoxysilyl) propyl]ethylenediamine (TPEDA) were used for CO₂ adsorption. The thermodynamic analysis indicated that the adsorption process is endothermic in 20-60 °C but is exothermic in 60-150 °C. The desorption time was 25 min at 120 °C, 30 min at 0.145 bar, or 7.5 min via a combination of thermal treatment and vacuum suction [10]. Impregnation of monoethanolamine (MEA) and 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) blocked most of the pores on activated carbon particles and resulted in the decrease of surface area. However, the amination of the adsorbent improved the uptake of CO₂ from 0.41 mmole/g to 1.11 mmole/g (MEA-treated) and 0.77 mmole/g (AMP-treated) [11]. Bhunia et al. [12] found that the uptake of CO₂ on porous covalent trizaine-based framework (PCTF) materials did not correlate with the heat of adsorption at zero coverage but related to the BET surface area and pore volume. The heat of adsorption ranged from 20-30 kJ/mole. The highest uptake of CO₂ was about 2.6 mmole/g at 0 °C and the CO₂/N₂ ratio (selectivity) was 41.

In this paper, the surface of ACFs were grafted with N-functionalities using MEA and TPEDA. The physicochemical properties of amine-grafted ACFs were characterized using several techniques and the adsorption performance of CO₂ on amine-grafted ACFs was investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this paper, the surface of ACFs were grafted with N-functionalities using MEA and TPEDA. One commercial PAN-based ACFs sample was used as the starting material (denoted as ACF). The ACF samples were pretreated at 100 °C for 24 h in vacuum to eliminate the moisture and other impurities before further modifications.

The MEA functionalization of ACFs were obtained by reflux method. The MEA (C₂H₇NO) was added to deionized water such that 7 M MEA solution was prepared. The pretreated ACF sample of about 2 g was added into 100 ml of MEA solution. The mixture was refluxed at the boiling temperature for 2 h. After cooling to room temperature, the fabric was washed with acetone and copious deionized water until the filtrate was close to neutral. The product was dried at 100 °C for 24 h and it was denoted as MEA-ACF. If the sample was oxidized before modified with MEA, it was denoted as cMEA-ACF. The oxidation of ACF samples was by treating with citric acid (C₆H₈O₇), as follows: 2 g of ACFs was added to 30 ml of the citric acid aqueous solution (1.6 mM) and subjected to 15 min ultrasonic treatment using a magnetic stirrer (46 kHz, 150 W), followed by impregnation for 24 h. The aqueous solution was removed and the samples were heat-treated in a muffle furnace at 300 °C for 30 min. The functionalization of TPEDA (C₈H₂₂N₂O₃Si) was conducted as follows [10]. 2 g of ACF samples were added into the flask with the TPEDA solutions (50 ml of 97 % TPEDA, 200 ml of 99.8 % toluene, and 16 ml of deionized water). The mixture was refluxed at boiling temperature for 2 h. After cooling to room temperature, the ACF sample was subsequently dried in a tubular furnace at 100 °C for 2 h and continued at 200 °C for 2 h with a ramp of 10 °C/min by passing N₂ gas of 100 sccm. The ACFs grafted with TPEDA was denoted as TPEDA-ACF.

The surface morphology of the samples was characterized using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, Hitachi S-4700). The elemental compositions of carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N) and the others were obtained through elemental analysis (EA, Elementar Vario EL III). The oxidation resistance of the samples was determined in flowing air (60 cm³/min) with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TA Instrument 5100). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and the measurements of N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to determine the number and type of functional groups present on the surface of the samples. The XPS spectra of all samples were obtained using a spectrophotometer (ESCA PHI 1600). The surface structure of the samples were probed by N₂

adsorption/desorption isotherms measured at -196 °C, carried out using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 accelerated surface and porosimetry analysis system.

The CO₂ adsorption isotherms of all samples were measured using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 accelerated surface and porosimetry analysis system at 25, 40 or 55 °C. Samples of about 0.15 g were outgassed at 350 °C for 240 min to remove adsorbed contaminants prior to the measurement. The equilibration interval for each pressure point was 45 seconds. The temperature during the CO₂ adsorption process was maintained by circular water bath thermostat. In this study, the Freundlich equation (Equation 1) was used to fit the experimental data,

$$q = K_F P^{1/n} \quad (1)$$

where q is amount of CO₂ adsorbed (mmole/g), P is the partial pressure of CO₂ (kPa), K_F is the adsorption equilibrium coefficient and n is a constant. The Freundlich isotherm is an empirical equation that assumes heterogeneous adsorption due to the diversity of adsorption sites. The CO₂/N₂ selectivity was determined to understand the interaction strength with active adsorption sites. The selectivity factors was defined as S_{ads} in Equation 2, where q_i is the uptake and p_i is the partial pressure of component i.

$$S_{ads} = \frac{q_1 / q_2}{p_1 / p_2} \quad (2)$$

Finally, the Clausius-Clapeyron equation (Equation 3) was used to calculate the isosteric heat of adsorption, where Q_{st} is the isosteric heat of adsorption (kJ/mole), R is the universal gas constant (8.314 J/mole/K), T is the absolute temperature (K) and A is a constant.

$$\ln P = A - \frac{Q_{st}}{R} \frac{1}{T} \quad (3)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterizations of the adsorbents

The FESEM images of the adsorbents are shown in Figure 1. The diameter of one single fiber as-received was approximately 6.8 μm and the surface was smooth with small cracks (Figure 1a). The ACFs aminated with MEA resulted in some pores generated on the surface (Figure 1b-c). Not only creating new pores but also grafting the thin films on the surface when the ACFs were modified with TPEDA (Figure 1d). The amination of ACFs did not change the diameters of the fibers. The EA was carried out to obtain the compositions of C, H, and N atoms in the samples. As seen from the data (Figure 2), element C was the most abundant constituent, between 75-84 wt. %. Since the basal structure of PAN-based ACFs featured the C≡N groups, the data interpreted the N content of about 3.66 wt. % in the as-received ACF. The amination of ACFs supplemented the N content to 4.89 wt. % (MEA-ACF), 4.82 wt. % (cMEA-ACF) and 3.95 wt. % (TPEDA-ACF). Except for C, H and N, the weight percent of the others decreased significantly when the ACFs were modified with MEA. The above discussion indicated that the modification of ACFs with MEA could create new pores, increase N content, and decrease the chemisorbed oxygen-containing species. Figure 3 depicted that the temperatures for the maximum rate of weight loss (or oxidation) for ACF, MEA-ACF, cMEA-ACF and TPEDA-ACF were 634, 602, 582 and 633 °C. The data indicated that the oxidation resistance weakened slightly as the ACFs were aminated. This could be attributed to the fact that the new pores were generated on the surface of ACFs. The oxidation followed by MEA treatment would enhance the destruction of the oxidation resistance. On the other hand, the TPEDA modification of ACFs was able to keep the strength of resistance, which could be due to the attachment of TPEDA chains on the surface of ACFs.

Figure 1: FESEM images of the samples.

Figure 2: Elemental compositions of the adsorbents.

The XPS survey scan spectra of the samples revealed that the major peaks in the scan spectra were due to the C1s, O1s, and N1s photoelectrons. The surface atomic ratios (N/C and O/C) derived from survey scan spectra were compared to see the nature of three samples. The N/C ratios were 0.027 (ACF), 0.028 (MEA-ACF), 0.044 (cMEA-ACF), and 0.141 (TPEDA-ACF), while the O/C ratios were 0.092 (ACF), 0.083 (MEA-ACF), 0.091 (cMEA-ACF), and 0.215 (TPEDA-ACF). The compositions on the surface were significantly different from those obtained from EA discussed previously. As seen from the data, the nitrogen atoms might penetrate into the interior of the ACFs during the amination with MEA; however, the TPEDA molecules were too bulky into the structure of ACFs such that a high concentration of N was observed on the surface. Table 1 shows the results of curve-fitting for the high resolution XPS N1s spectra for all samples. Deconvolution of the N1s spectra gives at most seven individual component groups. For ACF and MEA-ACF, the pyridine-type N and the quarternary N were the major N-functionality. Whilet the pyrrolic or amine moieties were the predominant groups on cMEA-ACF. It implied the pyridine-type structures would change to the pyridone structure at the oxygenated environment. It should be noted that the pyrrolic or amine moieties were overwhelmingly the most abundant species on TPEDA-ACF, which should be the attachment of the TPEDA molucules on the surface of ACFs such that the intrinsic properties of PAN-based ACFs were concealed.

Figure 3: TGA profiles of the adsorbents.

Table 1: Results of the fits of the XPS N 1s region, values given in at. % of total intensity

Sample	Binding energy (eV)						
	395.7	398.4	400.1	401.2	402.4	404	405
	Nitride-like species or aromatic N-imines (N _{G1})	Pyridine-type N (N _{G2})	Pyrrolic or amine moieties (or Pyrrole, Pyridone) (N _{G3})	Quarternary N (N _{G4})	Pyridine-N oxides (N _{G5})	Shake-up satellites (N _{G6})	NO ₂ (N _{G7})
ACF	0.0	23.1	17.9	22.5	9.9	2.1	24.4
MEA-ACF	0.2	27.8	19.1	21.3	12.4	0.0	19.2
cMEA-ACF	0.5	24.5	32.7	20.6	5.5	0.0	16.2
TPEDA-ACF	4.7	3.8	82.9	0.0	5.5	0.2	2.8

The N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms of the samples at -196 °C (Figure 4) indicated that the adsorption isotherms for all samples were essentially type I according to the BET classification and the desorption branch almost superimposed on the adsorption branch, indicative of microporosity. Table 2 presents the surface structure properties of the adsorbents determined from N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms. The specific surface areas (SSA) of ACF, MEA-ACF, cMEA-ACF and TPEDA-ACF were 904, 853, 792, and 766 m₂/g. As seen from the data, the amination of ACFs decreased the SSA and pore volumes slightly, consistent with Khalil et al. (2012). However, the micropore surface areas of the adsorbents significantly improved after amination, and the mesopore volumes increased for the ACFs modified with MEA. It was expected that the intrinsic pores on ACFs were blocked by TPEDA molecules such that the SSA and the pore volume on TPEDA-ACF were less than the other samples. The results implied the functionalization of N-groups for the surface of ACFs might expand the entrance of the pores, create new pores or block the original pores on the ACFs. Nevertheless, the ratio of the micropore area to the specific surface area increased followed the order TPEDA-ACF (0.744) > MEA-ACF (0.722) > cMEA-ACF (0.716) > ACF (0.512).

Figure 4: Adsorption isotherms of N₂ at 77 K for the samples.Table 2. Surface structure of the adsorbents determined from N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms.

	SSA (m ² /g)	Langmuir (m ² /g)	S _{mi} ^α (m ² /g)	V _t ^γ (cm ³ /g)	V _{mi} ^η (cm ³ /g)	V _{me} ^φ (cm ³ /g)	V _{ma} ^ξ (cm ³ /g)	Mean pore size ^ζ (nm)
ACF	904	1208	618	0.43	0.28	0.07	0.08	1.88
MEA-ACF	853	1143	825	0.41	0.25	0.09	0.07	1.94
cMEA-ACF	792	1061	760	0.38	0.23	0.08	0.07	1.92
TPEDA-ACF	766	1023	761	0.37	0.23	0.07	0.07	1.92

^α S_{mi} was determined by t-plot method. ^γ V_t represents the single point total pore volume at P/P₀ ≈ 0.99. ^η V_{mi} was determined by t-plot method. ^φ V_{me} was calculated by BJH method. ^ξ V_{ma} was found by subtracting V_{me} and V_{mi} from V_t. ^ζ Mean pore size was obtained by 4V/SSA.

3.2 Adsorption performance of CO₂

Figure 5 depicted the adsorption isotherms of CO₂ collected on the adsorbents at 25, 40 and 55 °C for low CO₂ pressures less than 120 kPa. The uptakes of CO₂ had typical monotonic curves, which were increasing with increasing pressures. It is clear that the adsorbed amounts decreased with increasing temperature, indicating that the CO₂ adsorption was an exothermic reaction. The adsorption amounts of CO₂ at 25 °C and 101.3 kPa (1 atm) followed the order ACF (2.358 mmole/g) > cMEA-ACF (2.215 mmole/g) > TPEDA-ACF (2.098 mmole/g) > MEA-ACF (1.964 mmole/g). At 40 and 55 °C, the uptake of CO₂ on TPEDA-ACF would surpass that on cMEA-ACF. The Freundlich equations could be used to fit the adsorption data well with R² > 0.999. The parameter *n* varied between 1.39-1.69, decreasing with increased temperature, indicative of the favorable adsorption.

In general, the adsorption selectivity of CO₂ over N₂ (CO₂/N₂ ratio) increased with increasing temperature. Only one exception is that the best CO₂/N₂ ratio on cMEA-ACF occurred at 40 °C. The CO₂/N₂ ratio was the highest on MEA-ACF at 25 °C (8.40), on TPEDA-ACF at 40 °C (9.15), and on MEA-ACF at 55 °C (9.66). This indicates the amination of ACFs was favorable for CO₂ adsorption and repelled the attraction with nitrogen molecules. The isosteric heats of adsorption (Q_{st}) for CO₂ adsorption on all adsorbents were in the range of 22-36 kJ/mole, implying the physical adsorption during the adsorption amounts of 0.2 – 1.2 mmole/g. The relationship between the Q_{st} and the amount of CO₂ adsorbed was decreased linearly if the amount of CO₂ adsorbed was on a log-scale. It is believed that the adsorption of CO₂ was occurred on heterogeneous surfaces, and the surface heterogeneity followed the order TPEDA-ACF > ACF > MEA-ACF > cMEA-ACF. The results showed that the amination of ACFs is favorable to as the adsorbents for CO₂ adsorption.

Figure 5: Adsorption isotherms of CO₂ for the samples.

Figure 6: Adsorption selectivity of CO₂/N₂ on the samples.

Figure 7: The isosteric heat of adsorption (Q_{st}) of CO_2 on the samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, except for surface modification, the amination of ACFs resulted in the generation of new pores or cracks on the surface of fibers, and the ratio of the micropore area to specific surface area increased. However, the new pores could be developed from the original micropores or part of the original pores on the ACFs were slightly destroyed or blocked such that the specific surface area and pore volume did not increase. Once the ACFs modified with MEA or TPEDA, the bulk N content increased. TPEDA-ACF exhibited the most abundant surface N atoms which could be attributed to one molecule of TPEDA has two nitrogen atoms. Additionally, the graft of MEA onto oxidized ACFs was favorable to the fixation of nitrogen functional groups on the surface. Moreover, TPEDA-ACF had the highest O/C ratio implying the improvement in hydrophilicity. To sum up, the ACF and MEA-grafted ACFs were characterized by the pyridine-like structures of six-member rings, while the pyrrolic or amine moieties were mainly introduced by the TPEDA modification. Pre-oxidation followed by MEA treatment of ACFs would lead the pyridine-like structures to change to the pyridone structures. The adsorption of CO_2 on all samples was indicative of physical adsorption and exothermic reactions. The Freundlich equations could be used to fit the adsorption data well and all indicated the favorable adsorption. The adsorption selectivity of CO_2 over N_2 was the best for MEA-ACF at $55\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (~ 9.7). The data also showed the adsorption of CO_2 was occurred on the heterogeneous surfaces. The results of this paper suggested that the aminated ACFs were the applicable adsorbents for CO_2 adsorption.

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